

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS.
PART XIII. AMPHOLYTIC INNER-METALLIC COBALTIC COMPLEXES
WITH NAPHTHYLBIGUANIDE *o*-SULPHONIC ACID AND PHENYL-
BIGUANIDE *p*-SULPHONIC ACID AND THEIR SALTS

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The ampholytic complex of trivalent cobalt with naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid has been prepared, and its alkali salts, as well as as those of the corresponding phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid complex, have been described.

In a previous paper (this issue, p. 563) the preparation and properties of the alkali salts of the ampholytic complexes of bivalent copper and nickel with naphthyl and phenylbiguanide sulphonic acids have been described. The present paper deals with the study of the alkali salts of the corresponding trivalent cobalt complexes.

The octahedral ampholytic cobaltic complexes with α -naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid or phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid might exist in two geometrical forms.

This arises from the difference in the relative positions of the aromatic groups to each other in the molecule. But only one form of the complex in each case has actually been isolated.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *Cobaltic Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonic Acid*.—Naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid (4.5 g.) was dissolved in an excess of warm concentrated ammonia; to this a solution of cobalt chloride (1g.) was added, followed by a solution of H_2O_2 . The precipitate, first formed, changed from light rose to brown. The mixture was heated and filtered. To the filtrate a vigorous current of air was passed for about 24 hours. The mixture was then evaporated on the water-bath till there was no smell of ammonia. On cooling, a brown precipitate separated. This was washed first with water, then with alcohol, and finally dried in air. {Found: N, 19.36; Co, 5.42. $Co(HO_2S.Nap.Big)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ requires N, 19.36; Co, 5.45 per cent}. $Nap.Big.H =$ a molecule of naphthylbiguanide.

The substance forms brown crystals, slightly soluble in water and dilute ammonia, but readily in caustic alkali,

2. *Potassium Cobaltic Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonate*.—Cobaltic naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid (4 g.) was dissolved in moderately concentrated solution of KOH. The solution was concentrated on the water-bath. On the addition of alcohol to the cold solution a brown precipitate separated out. This was purified by dissolving it in the least quantity of water and then reprecipitating with absolute alcohol. It was washed first with 90% alcohol, then with absolute alcohol, and finally dried in air. {Found: N, 17.91; Co, 4.98; K, 9.95. $K_3[Co(SO_3.Nap.Big)_2] \cdot 5H_2O$ requires N, 17.82; Co, 5.0; K, 9.93 per cent}.

The substance forms brown crystals, highly soluble in water. It reacts alkaline to litmus.

3. *Sodium cobaltic naphthylbiguanide o-sulphonate* was prepared like the potassium salt by substituting NaOH for KOH. It resembles the latter salt in properties. {Found : N, 19.57 ; Co, 5.48 ; Na, 6.44. $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{SO}_3\text{NapBig})_3] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 19.55 ; Co, 5.49 ; Na, 6.43 per cent }.

4. *Potassium cobaltic phenylbiguanide p-sulphonate* was prepared like the potassium salt of the corresponding naphthylbiguanide complex. It forms highly soluble brown powder. {Found : N, 20.96 ; Co, 5.90 ; K, 11.68. $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{O}_3\text{S. PhBig})_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 21.06 ; Co, 5.91 ; K, 11.72 per cent }.

5. *Sodium cobaltic phenylbiguanide p-sulphonate* was prepared in the same way as the sodium salt of the corresponding naphthylbiguanide complex, and it resembles the latter in properties. {Found : N, 20.61 ; Co, 5.76 ; Na, 6.71. $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{O}_3\text{S. PhBig})_3] \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 30.61 ; Co, 5.79 ; Na, 6.77 per cent }. PhBigH = a molecule of phenylbiguanide.

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Received June 29, 1948.